

DEVELOPMENT OF TERROR-RELATED TRAUMA SCALE AS A CULTURALLY SENSITIVE TOOL FOR THE ASSESSMENT OF TERROR-RELATED TRAUMA

Nanlir ZINGFA¹ and Joshua Chiroma GANDI²

¹Plateau State University, Bokokos

²Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna

Phone no: 08109657583. Email: zingfananlir@plasu.edu.ng

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria, a country in Africa, has experienced and continues to experience various forms of armed conflict, including banditry, Boko Haram insurgency, farmers–herders clashes, and other forms of organized violence. One of the major consequences of these conflicts is terror-related trauma, which manifests in diverse psychological symptoms among affected populations. This study aimed to develop a culturally relevant Terror-Related Trauma Scale suitable for use by practitioners and researchers in assessing trauma symptoms among war survivors in Nigeria. A mixed-method research design was employed, and data were collected from 230 participants, comprising males and females across different age groups. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was conducted to examine the construct validity of the scale. Preliminary analyses confirmed the adequacy of the data for factor analysis (Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin = .846; Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity, $p < .001$). The initial EFA of 23 items revealed a two-factor structure, supported by eigenvalues and the scree plot. Three items that failed to load adequately were removed, and a second-phase EFA conducted on the remaining 20 items yielded a clear and interpretable two-factor solution with minimal cross-loadings. Reliability analysis indicated good internal consistency for the final 20-item scale, with a Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of .86. Item–total statistics further showed that all Terror-Related Trauma Scale has satisfactory psychometric properties, supporting its use for research and applied psychological assessment in conflict-affected settings in Nigeria.

Keywords: Terror-related trauma, scale development, exploratory factor analysis, reliability, armed conflict, Nigeria

Background to the Study

In the context of psychology, trauma refers to any event/situation that overwhelms an individual’s coping ability and leads to feelings of helplessness, fear, or horror. This painful or distressing phenomenon, which emerges through an experience of adversity, causes a lasting detrimental effect to mental, social, or emotional wellbeing. Trauma has been long recognized as a complex construct, with some differentiation being made between experiencing one-off adversities (Type 1 trauma) or repeated complex traumas (Type 2 trauma) (Briere & Gil, 1998). Psychological trauma remains a global mental health challenge triggered by common events such as road accidents (Bisan et al., 2024), non-partner violence (Adesina et al., 2019) and inter-partner violence, all of which have high rates of occurrence and generate significant mental health problems (Bisan et al., 2024).

Nigeria is a highly populated country in Africa with multi-ethno-religious characteristics which had experienced and still experiencing series of armed conflicts. The resulting rise in armed conflicts can be attributed to various factors, including: ethnic rivalry, religious violence, land conflicts, conflicts related to the demarcation of administrative boundaries and political elections, and conflicts linked to oil production in the Niger Delta. Most disturbing of it all is the persistent

herder-farmer crises that is spreading like wild fire across all nooks and crannies of Nigeria. Typical source of trauma has been the intractable and unwarranted farmer-herder conflicts in some parts of Benue, Nasarawa, Plateau and Taraba States which according to Hagher (2013) have attracted wide condemnations and lamentations.

Statement of the Problem

Psychological traumas in Nigeria have mostly been sequel to the effects of terrorism, banditry, kidnapping, and farmer-herder conflicts. These unfortunate war-like developments have been claiming thousands of lives, destroying government properties, eroding mutual trusts, and inflicting traumatic experience among survivors. Therefore, there is need cogent to measure such aftermath of war (trauma) on the populist and its consequences in Nigeria. Despite the importance of assessment for effective intervention in such cases, there seems to be lack of a suitable and culturally sensitive scale. Most of the psychological scales that relate to this target area were developed in other jurisdictions outside Nigeria which might not be culturally appropriate. Therefore, there is cogent need to develop a psychometrically suitable war-related trauma scale that would be adjudged culturally sensitive for assessing terror-related trauma in middle belt and Nigeria as a whole.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The study's theoretical framework hinges on the psychometric theories, typically classical test theory and item response theory, being commonly applied as the informative framework that gauge test development process. Classical test theory (CTT) is a foundational framework built on the premise that any observed score on a psychological test is composed of a true score and an error score (Lord & Novick, 1968). The true score reflects the individual's actual ability or trait, while the error score accounts for random variations that can affect the test results (or outcomes). In the context of psychological test development, it provides essential tools and concepts for evaluating and refining test items, ensuring that the final test is both reliable and valid. Item response theory (IRT) is a modern psychometric framework widely used in the development and analysis of psychological tests. Pioneered by Lord et al. (1968), it focuses on the relationship between latent traits (i.e. unobservable characteristics) and the item responses (Lord et al., 1968; Birnbaum, 1968). The probability of a particular response to an item is a function of both the individual's latent trait and specific item parameters (e.g. difficulty, discrimination, guessing) and allows for more nuanced and precise measurement, offering insights into how individual items perform across different levels of the trait being measured (Embretson & Reise, 2000). The emphasis of IRT on item-level analysis provides several advantages for psychological test development.

TRAUMA THEORIES

The study further hinges on the stress response theory and the shattered assumption theory to explain the variable of study. The stress response theory by Horowitz (1976, 1986) explains how traumatic event impact human sanity. The central idea of this theory is that a when something unpleasant occur, it influence one's cognition. And this effect depends on how the affected individual manages all the numerous thoughts and feelings within him, and this will determine whether the person involved would be diagnosed with post-traumatic stress disorder or not. Horowitz (1976) further asserted that the inability to process the trauma experiences often leads to constant post-traumatic reactions as the information reside in the individual memory and persistently surface into awareness in the form of nightmares, flashbacks and intrusions. Similarly, the theory of shattered assumptions developed by Janoff-Bulman (1992) buttress on the influence of worldview in psychological efforts by the person to keep and enhance perceptions of stability and control after occurrence of traumatic events. The individual develop some essential yet, silent

assumptions about themselves and the world they live in. According to the shattered assumption theory, the assumptions are in three folds, namely: the world is benevolent or kind, the self is worthy and the world is meaningful. The worldview provide an individual with self esteem, meaning of life and helps clear misconceptions. Based on this theory, individual worldviews changes when traumatic events occurs. This mandate the individual to changes those assumption and perception of the world. The implication of this consequence of confusion, defenseless, awareness of insecurity, lead physiological reactivity and anxiety that characterize post-traumatic stress disorder (Janoff-Bulman 1992).

METHOD

Research Design

The exploratory sequential mixed method design which has been considered most suitable for studies that focus on developing and validating psychological test was adopted in this case. It uses feasible approach that begins with the collection and analysis of qualitative data which helps to explore a phenomenon in-depth and generate insights that inform subsequent quantitative test. According to Creswell et al. (2003) exploratory sequential design is best suited for exploring a phenomenon and often best used for developing and testing instruments as well as enhancing ease of generalizing the instrument's assessment outcomes to different groups (Morgan, 1998).

Study Population and Sample

The study target population consists of male and female Nigerians who were exposed to war related situations at Bokkos, Mangu, Barkin Ladi, Riyom and Bassa LGAs in Plateau state. Based on Tinsley and Tinsley (1987)'s suggestion for a ratio of between 5 to 10 participants per item, a sample of 230 persons participated as respondents in this test development.

Instrumentation (Scale Development)

The war-related trauma scale development process adopted an emergent test development format established by Gregory (2017). The specific stages include: defining the test, selecting representative scaling method, constructing the items, testing the items, revising the items, and publishing the test.

Defining the test

Terror related trauma scale is an instrument that aims at measuring experience from war related situations. The target participants for the scale are adult of different age group, religious affiliation, level of education and socio-economic status. However, people with disabilities who had experience war related situation can also take the test. This instrument can also be translated to the language of the test-takers by the test user without altering with any of the items. The scales measure all terror related situations. Participants will respond to this instrument on a multiple-choice format specifically on the Likert options.

Selecting representative scaling method

The study adopted Likert scales, which is one of the already established scaling method developed by Likert (1932). In particular, the 5-point using adaptable response format initially developed for measuring attitudes is the scale of choice. These five response options alongside their respective scoring weights include: Strongly Agree (SA) = 5, Agree (A) = 4, Undecided (U) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2, and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1. Final score can be obtained by summing up responses across all items of the scale and interpretation will be based on mean score.

Constructing the items

Being an emergent test development, items are devised and derived mostly from appropriate primary sources. The particular methods used in this case include individual interview and empirical review. Interview was conducted with a sample that consisted of 10 participants (n=10) who had experienced war situation in Nigeria, including both males and females (M=6; F=4), based on their level of response saturation.

Testing the items

In this study, testing the items is necessary since Gregory (2017) affirmed that the test items will be more robust and of high standard if interrogated using different ways. Hence, both qualitative and quantitative methods are adopted in interrogating the items being developed for this study.

Qualitative test of items: The transcribed items are administered for review by expert reviewers, including post graduate students and graduate assistants at the department of psychology, Plateau state University Bokkos, as well as subject matter experts in the field of trauma psychology. Following their reviews, a number of items were recommended for deletion because they appeared not to measure the target constructs as required. The completion of qualitative review led to retaining 23 items which are considered for further refining based on quantitative method.

Quantitative test of items: Consequently, 20 items at the stage of item quantitative analysis met the criteria for inclusion in the final test.

Revising the items

Resulting from both the qualitative and quantitative item tests, some of the items survived the process as they are but other modification or alteration while some seem completely irrelevant and considered for deletion. This is the rationale for appropriate item revision in order to improve the overall test quality. According to Gregory (2017), there is need to ensure such appropriate item revisions, test structure adjustment, and expert final reviews as part of developing a new test.

Publishing the test

Publishing the test, at this level of its development stage, focuses only on presenting and submitting manuscript as an article that describes the terror-related trauma scale empirical development process. The final process of “publishing the test” will be conducted after final thorough “scale validation” which is the second phase of producing a complete standardized psychological scale.

Data Collection and Analysis Method

The data collection procedure commenced by obtaining a formal letter of introduction from the Plateau State University Department of Psychology, which facilitated gaining approval and data collection permission at the study sites. Participants were duly informed about the study objectives and process as well as their anticipated respective roles as individual voluntary respondents. Those who willingly consented to participate were further assured of their privacy and confidentiality of any information to be provided by them. The instrument being developed was then to the individual participants and they willingly responded as required. At the point of retrieving the completed forms, they were appreciated for their time and kind participation which goes a long way in ensuring the completion of this test development. All retrieved test forms were then collated and coded for onward item analysis that would towards test revision and other process thereafter. Both descriptive and inferential analyses were conducted by adopting Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin, KMO

and Barlett’s test of sphericity, Cronbach’s alpha and factor loading for each item, item-total statistics, reliability statistics, and the scale statistics.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

This test development study followed empirical methodology which include human participants at some points. Therefore, all appropriate ethical considerations were adhered to and complied with as required. The formal letter of introduction from the Plateau State University, dated 28th May 2025, based on the authority of the University vested in the Head of Psychology Department (see Appendix A), herein also dully served as authentic ethical clearance approval in this case.

RESULT

DESCRIPTIVE RESULT

This section presents the descriptive statistics of the study variables, summarizing respondents’ mean scores and standard deviations across the scale items (Table1). The results provide an overview of the general response patterns and the distribution of Terror-related trauma experiences among the participants.

Table 1
Scale Descriptive Statistics (N = 230)

Item	Mean	Std. Deviation
ITEM1	2.57	1.439
ITEM2	2.11	1.179
ITEM3	2.55	1.158
ITEM4	2.40	1.154
ITEM5	1.65	1.046
ITEM6	1.74	1.183
ITEM7	2.85	1.404
ITEM8	3.70	1.283
ITEM9	2.69	1.266
ITEM10	2.83	1.263
ITEM11	2.73	1.239
ITEM12	2.19	1.232
ITEM13	2.51	1.260
ITEM14	3.20	1.312
ITEM15	3.24	1.339
ITEM16	3.02	1.278
ITEM17	2.91	1.247
ITEM18	2.80	1.300
ITEM19	2.79	1.348
ITEM20	2.94	1.348
ITEM21	2.76	1.321
ITEM22	2.73	1.314
ITEM23	2.59	1.304

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for the 23 items of the scale based on responses from 230 participants. The item mean scores ranged from 1.65 to 3.70, indicating varying levels of endorsement across the items.

The standard deviation values ranged from 1.05 to 1.44, reflecting a moderate level of variability in responses across all items. The descriptive results indicate that respondents experienced varying degrees of Terror-related trauma, with certain symptoms being more prominent than others. The observed variability across items supports the suitability of the scale for capturing differential trauma experiences within the study population.

VALIDITY

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin and Bartlett’s Test

The Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) measure and Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity were conducted to assess the suitability of the data for Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA). The KMO statistic evaluates sampling adequacy, while Bartlett’s Test examines whether the correlation matrix is significantly different from an identity matrix. Together, these tests determine whether the data meet the necessary assumptions for conducting Exploratory Factor Analysis.

Table 2

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin and Bartlett’s Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.846
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1503.444
	Df	253
	Sig.	<.001

Result of Table 6 showed that the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy (KMO) and Bartlett’s test of sphericity. The Kaiser -Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy (KMO) and Barletts test of sphericity was used to test the suitability of data obtained from the scale items for the factor analysis. The KMO value was .846; Barlett’s test value $\chi^2=1503.444$; $df=253$ ($p <.001$) is accepted based on Keiser (1974) rule of thumb. Findings on the scale based on these recommendations show that the data are appropriate for factor analysis.

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was conducted to establish the construct validity of the instrument by examining the underlying factor structure of the measured variables. EFA was considered appropriate at this stage because the study sought to identify latent dimensions that account for the observed correlations among items.

Exploratory Factor Analysis Phase I

Initial Total Variance (23 Items)

The initial total variance explained for the 23 items indicates that Factor 1 had an eigenvalue of 5.85, accounting for 25.44% of the total variance, while Factor 2 had an eigenvalue of 2.14, explaining an additional 9.29% of the variance. Collectively, the first two factors accounted for 34.73% of the total variance in the initial solution. In line with the Kaiser criterion and supported by the scree plot, only the first two factors were considered substantial and retained for further analysis. This pattern suggests that the majority of the shared variance among the 23 items is captured by the two dominant underlying dimensions.

Pattern Matrix

Results of the EFA for the 23 items using maximum likelihood extraction with Promax rotation and Kaiser normalization yielded a two-factor solution, with rotation converging after three iterations. Factor loadings $\geq .30$ were considered salient for interpretation. Factor 1 was defined by strong to moderate loadings from Item8 (.43), Item10 (.44), Item14 (.51), Item15 (.32), Item16 (.55), Item17 (.35), Item18 (.53), Item19 (.65), Item20 (.77), Item21 (.68), Item22 (.70), and Item23 (.54). These items loaded primarily on Factor 1, suggesting a coherent underlying construct reflected by these indicators. Factor 2 was characterized by substantial loadings from Item1 (.36), Item2 (.58), Item3 (.32), Item4 (.33), Item5 (.81), Item6 (.84), Item12 (.33), and Item13 (.41). The strongest contributors to this factor were Item5 and Item6, indicating that they are central indicators of the second latent dimension.

Items 7, 9, and 11 did not load saliently on either factor (i.e., loadings $< .30$) and may therefore be considered weak indicators of the underlying constructs. As such, items that did not load adequately were excluded from further analysis. Specifically, Items 7, 9, and 11. Consequently, these items were removed and not included in the second phase of the EFA.

Exploratory Factor Analysis Phase II

Initial Total Variance (20 Items)

Following the exclusion of three items due to poor factor loadings, the Exploratory Factor Analysis was re-conducted on the remaining 20 items using maximum likelihood extraction. The total variance explained table indicates that two factors were retained, consistent with the Kaiser criterion and the scree plot. In the initial solution, Factor 1 had an eigenvalue of 5.65, accounting for 28.27% of the total variance, while Factor 2 had an eigenvalue of 2.12, explaining an additional 10.58% of the variance. Together, the two factors accounted for 38.85% of the total variance in the initial eigenvalue solution for the 20 items.

After extraction, the two-factor model explained a cumulative variance of 32.48%, with Factor 1 accounting for 25.07% and Factor 2 accounting for 7.42% of the variance. Following Promax rotation, the variance was redistributed across the factors, with rotated sums of squared loadings of 4.56 for Factor 1 and 3.51 for Factor 2. As the factors were allowed to correlate, the rotated variance values are not additive. Overall, these findings indicate that the refined 20-item instrument demonstrates a clear and interpretable two-factor structure, with the retained factors explaining a meaningful proportion of the total variance and providing further support for the construct validity of the scale.

Pattern Matrix

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) on the remaining 20 items using maximum likelihood extraction with an oblique Promax rotation (Kaiser normalization) revealed that the rotation converged after three iterations. Consistent with common practice, factor loadings of .30 and above were considered meaningful for interpretation. The analysis supported a two-factor solution. Factor 1 was defined by salient loadings from Item8 (.43), Item 10 (.44), Item 14 (.52), Item 15 (.32), Item 16 (.56), Item 17 (.35), Item 18 (.54), Item 19 (.65), Item 20 (.78), Item 21 (.69), Item 22 (.70), and Item 23 (.53) and this factor is label as Avoidance, Emotional distress and cognitive changes. These items loaded moderately to strongly on Factor 1, indicating a well-defined latent dimension represented by this set of items.

Factor 2 comprised Item 1 (.35), Item 2 (.59), Item 3 (.32), Item 4 (.32), Item 5 (.80), Item 6 (.84), Item 12 (.33), and Item 13 (.42) and is label as intrusion and hyperarousal symptoms. Item5 and

Item6 showed particularly strong loadings, suggesting that they are central indicators of the second factor. Overall, the pattern matrix indicates clear factorial separation, with no substantial cross-loadings observed. The results provide evidence for a stable two-factor structure, supporting the construct validity of the instrument under investigation (Table 3)

Table 3

Pattern Matrix for the 20-Item Scale

Item	Factor 1 (Avoidance, Emotional distress and cognitive changes)	Factor 2 (Intrusion and hyperarousal symptoms)
Item1		.350
Item2		.593
Item3		.317
Item4		.322
Item5		.797
Item6		.835
Item8	.433	
Item10	.439	
Item12		.326
Item13		.420
Item14	.518	
Item15	.322	
Item16	.555	
Item17	.349	
Item18	.536	
Item19	.647	
Item20	.776	

Item21	.685
Item22	.697
Item23	.532

RELIABILITY

Following the establishment of construct validity through Exploratory Factor Analysis, the 20 items retained after EFA were used to assess the internal consistency reliability of the instrument. Reliability was evaluated using Cronbach’s alpha to determine the extent to which the validated items consistently measure the underlying constructs. Item–total statistics were examined to further assess the internal consistency of the instrument by evaluating the relationship between each item and the overall scale score. This analysis provides insight into the contribution of individual items to the reliability of the scale and helps determine whether any item weakens the overall internal consistency (Table 4).

Table 4

Item–Total Statistics for the 20-Item Scale

Item	Corrected Item–Total Correlation	Cronbach’s Alpha if Item Deleted
Item1	.422	.855
Item2	.362	.857
Item3	.387	.856
Item4	.314	.858
Item5	.445	.854
Item6	.418	.855
Item8	.203	.863
Item10	.424	.854
Item12	.373	.856
Item13	.353	.857
Item14	.480	.852
Item15	.432	.854
Item16	.398	.855
Item17	.426	.854
Item18	.540	.850
Item19	.596	.847
Item20	.592	.847
Item21	.620	.846
Item22	.620	.846
Item23	.536	.850

The item–total statistics indicate that the 20-item scale demonstrates good internal consistency. Corrected item–total correlation values ranged from .203 to .620, with the majority of items exceeding the commonly accepted minimum threshold of .30, suggesting that most items contribute adequately to the overall scale. Items 18 to 22 showed particularly strong corrected

item–total correlations ($r = .54-.62$), indicating that they are highly consistent with the underlying construct measured by the scale. Item8 recorded a comparatively lower corrected item–total correlation (.203); however, its removal would result in only a marginal increase in Cronbach’s alpha ($\alpha = .863$), suggesting that retaining the item does not substantially compromise the overall reliability of the instrument.

The “Cronbach’s alpha if item deleted” values ranged from .846 to .863, and none of the items, if deleted, would result in a substantial improvement in the overall alpha coefficient. This pattern indicates that all retained items contribute meaningfully to the scale, and there is no empirical justification for further item deletion.

Overall, the reliability analysis yielded a Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of .86 for the 20-item scale, indicating good internal consistency. This value exceeds the commonly accepted threshold of .70, suggesting that the items reliably measure the underlying constructs. The result demonstrates that the instrument possesses adequate reliability and is suitable for use in subsequent analyses. Overall, the findings support the internal consistency reliability of the instrument, confirming that the 20 EFA-validated items form a reliable measure of the underlying constructs.

DISCUSSION

In order to determine the reliability level of terror-related trauma scale, Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient as the criterion of internal consistency (Tavşancıl, 2005) was used. It was conducted with 230 war survivors and found to be .86, implying the scale is appropriate for measuring terror related trauma. Analysis of individual items indicated that the items have good factor loading. This corroborates that the scale development followed methodical process which objective synthesis and calibration of items. The terror-related trauma scale was found to be reliability. Development of this culturally sensitive scale will enable researchers, practitioner and government to understand the psychological, emotional and social needs of conflict-affected populations in Nigeria. The results revealed that the a 20-item terror-related trauma scale, based on 5-point Likert scaling, with highly significant content validity. Final thorough validation of the scale is recommended to establish detailed construct validity, criterion validity, and other complements of psychometric properties that makes a test standardized and highly adaptable. Thereafter, researchers and test users can adapt the scale to enhance cultural specificity of their various testing situations as required in different contexts.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study only focuses only on exploratory factor analysis which is just a preliminary stage in test development without conducting confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) which is a final stage in psychometric evaluations, including test–retest reliability, convergent and divergent validity. As such, the scale is not yet a finalized instrument.

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APPENDIX A: ETHICAL CLEARANCE LETTER

PLATEAU STATE UNIVERSITY, BOKKOS

FACULTY OF SOCIAL SCIENCES
DEPARTMENT OF PSYCHOLOGY

28th May, 2025.

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

ZINGFA HANLIR With matriculation number PLASU/2023/MSC/PSY/0010
is a Post Graduate student in the department of Psychology Plateau state
University Bokkos, undertaking research work on..... DEVELOPMENT OF
..... WJAR - RELATED TRAUMA SCALE IN NIGERIA

Kindly accord him/her all the necessary assistance he/she needs for the success of
the research work.

Thank you,

Date: 28/5/2025

Dr. Dauda Akwai Saleh
HOD PSYCHOLOGY

APPENDIX B

Final Items that were Included after Qualitative and Quantitative Analysis

1	I find it difficult to sleep at night
2	I sleep excessively (too much) even during working hours or school time
3	I frequently struggle to pay close attention and concentrate
4	I avoid conversations with people
5	I find myself contemplating suicide
6	I find myself contemplating murder
7	I am conscious of any environment I find myself
8	I am prompted by every circumstance similar to war within me
9	I feel guilty even if I did no wrong
10	I have the feelings of distrust in me
11	I feel the world is not a safe place
12	I can't remember anything good that happens during the crisis
13	I am terrified by any loud sound
14	I distance myself when people are discussing about wars
15	I try avoiding environment or places that looks like my previous places.
16	The experience of the war keeps reoccurring to me (especially when am playing with peers)
17	I often feel the crisis is happening again.
18	I have terrible dreams (nightmare) about what happen to me in the past.
19	I often have disturbing dreams about the war
20	I often have headache since after the crisis